

PERFORMANCE OF PV ARRAYS WITH BIFACIAL PV MODULES INSTALLED IN EAST-WEST STRUCTURES FOR RELIABLE IRRIGATION APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT: Bifacial PV technology contributes to increasing energy production in PV facilities compared with mono-facial PV modules, using the same occupied surface. Applications such as PV pumping for irrigation can also take advantage of using bifacial PV modules if the design of the PV system is adapted. Professional irrigation in agriculture requires water production during the dry season and constant operation during the day to maintain a regular flow and pressure, mainly in direct irrigation systems. Static support structures oriented to west and east (EW) with tilt angle of 60° reach energy profiles adapted to the irrigation needs and constitute a reliable solution compared to other systems, such as trackers. Bifacial PV modules installed in such EW structures can improve the performance and increase energy production for PV irrigation, meeting the technical requirements and maintaining a high degree of reliability of the system. This paper reports on the characterization of an EW static structure using bifacial PV modules, the so-called EWB(60). Measurements from a prototype installed in the facilities of the IES-UPM in Madrid have been taken over a full year of sun exposure using two bifacial PV modules, previously calibrated, with the aim of recording irradiance and cell temperature. The results provide some key conclusions in terms of energy production, constancy of the daily energy profile and the evaluation of the energy losses.

1 INTRODUCTION

PV technology applied to irrigation must guarantee quality in terms of water supply and be capable of maintaining constant flow and pressure regimes, as close as possible to the service provided by the electrical grid [1]. However, the variation of solar radiation throughout the day and the solar intermittency caused by passing clouds [2], are a limitation to meet optimal irrigation requirements compared to the paradigm of the electrical grid. One of the improvements introduced for water pumping stability in PV irrigation has been the employment of horizontal north - south axis trackers (1xh) [3] which, during the irrigation periods, mainly in summertime, are able to generate horizontal daily energy profiles in clear sky days [4] instead of the bell-shaped energy profiles generated by equator oriented static structures (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Effective irradiance of two different supporting structures: one horizontal north - south axis tracker (1xh) and one equator (south) oriented static structure with tilt angle of 25° (S25). Both curves have been obtained with the simulation tool SISIFO (www.sisifo.info) in Madrid (40.39N, -3.63W) on June 17 using as meteorological data the typical meteorological year (TMY).

Trackers allow a constant daily energy profile in summertime sunny days and extend the available hours for irrigation [1]. However, trackers present maintenance needs [5] that static structures do not have, and this is an issue for stand-alone applications in remote and decentralized areas with lack of operation and

maintenance structures. To solve that, a previous work presented a solution to reach horizontal daily energy profiles employing static structures [6], which do not present maintenance needs. The so-called delta structure, $\Delta S(\beta)$, is a static structure made up of two halves, one oriented to the east and the other one to the west, achieving a constant irradiance daily profile similar to that obtained by a 1xh tracker when the tilted angle of PV modules is $\beta = 60^\circ$. To evaluate the constancy of the irradiance daily profile, that work proposed a “constancy index”, k_c , based on the coefficient of variation (CV) of such irradiance:

$$k_c = 1 - CV = 1 - \frac{\sigma}{\mu} = 1 - \frac{\sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \mu)^2}}{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N x_i} \quad (1)$$

for a given time series of N values, and x_i describing a general variable profile, where μ and σ are the mean and the standard deviation respectively. k_c values close to 1 indicates daily plane irradiance profiles.

The work published in [6] reported a $k_c = 0.98$, measured at the latitude of Madrid on a clear sky day close to the summer solstice. It must be noted that $\Delta S(60)$ applied to irrigation requires a peak power higher than that needed in a 1xh tracker to achieve the same water volume that an 1xh during the irrigation period, but lower than that needed in a S25 : 1.75 for $\Delta S(60)$ and 2 for S25 (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Hourly water pumped volume for 1xh and $\Delta S(60)$ structures in Madrid (40.39N, -3.63W) on June 17,

simulated with SISIFO and using TMY.

Performance of such east-west PV structures applied in water pumping systems for irrigation can be improved using bifacial PV modules. This technology installed in such structures can increase energy production, while meeting PV irrigation technical requirements and maintaining a high degree of system reliability.

This paper reports on the performance of a new concept of east-west structure using bifacial PV modules, the so-called EWB(β). A prototype has been installed on the rooftop of the Solar Energy Institute of the Technical University of Madrid (IES-UPM) facilities in Madrid and measurements have been taken using two bifacial PV modules, previously calibrated and transformed into reference modules, with the aim of recording the front and rear irradiances and cell temperatures of both halves over a full year of sun exposure.

The experiment has been useful to characterize this new design concept, obtaining results such as quantifying the energy gain compared to the delta structure and evaluating both the constancy index and the energy losses when using just a single maximum power point tracker (MPPT) due to the different operating temperatures of the PV modules of each half.

2 EAST-WEST STRUCTURE WITH BIFACIAL PV MODULES CONCEPT

The concept is similar to the $\Delta S(\beta)$ basis. It is a ground-mounted structure with half of the PV array oriented to the east and the other half to the west, both parts with the same tilt angle ($\beta = 60$). However, the two halves must be separated, as shown in Figure 3, to allow that the PV modules' rear sides obtain a good irradiation uptake, capturing both the albedo and global solar irradiation.

Figure 3: $\Delta S(60)$ and EWB(60) structure concepts.

The tilt angle $\beta = 60$ allows that the in-plane direct irradiance (B) on the front sides is close to constant during the period comprising 4 hours before and 4 hours after solar noon, which leads to in-plane global irradiance (G) reasonably approaching constancy for 8 hours per day. To obtain the total irradiance measured by both bifacial PV modules, the part captured by the rear sides must be added to such direct irradiance.

The experiment carried-out on the IES-UPM rooftop has been conceived to measure the front and rear sides in-plane irradiances and the cell temperatures in both east and west oriented PV modules throughout a full year with measuring slots of 5 minutes. Two bifacial PV modules (manufacturer JASOLAR, STC power $P^* = 370 \text{ Wp}$) have been modified to convert them into bifacial reference modules [7] working as sensors to measure front irradiance (G_{FRONT}), rear irradiance (G_{REAR}) and bifacial cell temperature (T_c) just dividing the module electrically into three parts [8]. The two end parts are short-circuited through calibrated resistances. A black vinyl sheet is directly glued onto the front (rear) side and then, protected with a white vinyl sheet (see Figure 4). This way, the

corresponding short-circuit current, $I_{SC,REAR}$ ($I_{SC,FRONT}$), becomes sensitive to only G_{REAR} (G_{FRONT}). The central part is left as open-circuit [9] running as a sensor of cell temperature.

Figure 4: Bifacial 60° tilt angle east-west prototype EWB(60). IES-UPM facilities (Madrid).

3 RESULTS

3.1 Energy gain

Energy increase achieved using bifacial PV modules can be analyzed just comparing solar irradiance measured on both front and rear sides with that measured only on the front sides of both PV modules of the EWB(60) prototype.

Figure 5 shows the set of irradiance profiles measured by the prototype on July 20, 2022, in a clear sky day. It can be appreciated the front and rear irradiances ($G_{E,FRONT}$, $G_{W,FRONT}$, $G_{E,REAR}$ and $G_{W,REAR}$) of both PV modules and the sum of all of them (G_{TOTAL} in W/m^2).

The EWB(60) gain in terms of solar irradiation (Wh/m^2) compared with only the front sides in this particular day is 20.7% (note that a bifaciality factor equal to 1 has been considered).

Figure 5: Solar irradiance profiles corresponding to the front and rear sides of each bifacial PV module in EWB(60), and total irradiance integrating all the system, measured on July 20, 2022.

Taking into account the measurements corresponding to the hypothetical irrigation period (here considered as the period between March and September equinoxes in the Northern Hemisphere), the total energy gain of the EWB(60) structure has been 21.5%.

These results must be underlined since energy gains in PV systems with bifacial technology but without changes in the design of the support structure, such as equator-oriented static structures, can simply achieve 5-7% more energy [10].

3.2 Constancy index.

The constancy index k_c has been obtained for each day of the year. It has been measured over the total irradiance (G_{TOTAL}) for the central 8 hours of each day (4 hours before and after noon).

Taking the measurements of July 20, 2022, shown in Figure 5, the corresponding constancy index has been $k_c = 0.91$. However, this figure is lower than that achieved if considering only the front sides, whose constancy index in this particular day would be $k_c = 0.96$. The reason for such a difference, as can be observed in Figure 5, is the effect of adding the rear side irradiances to G_{TOTAL} , producing two peaks, one in the morning and other one in the afternoon.

k_c values have been extracted from the irradiation profiles for each day of the year, as shown in Figure 6. Points below 0.8 indicates cloudy days or seasons with low solar declination (winter, and part of spring and autumn), while points greater than 0.8 correspond to days of clearer skies, which are concentrated in the summer season. The mean value of the latter has been calculated, $\mu(k_c) = 0.89$, and maximum k_c value was reached on July 14, 2022, with $k_{c,max} = 0.95$.

In the same way, looking at the results obtained considering only the front faces, the mean value would be $\mu(k_c) = 0.91$ and the maximum $k_{c,max} = 0.97$.

Figure 6: Distribution of the measured k_c values for each day of the year. Points under 0.8 indicate cloudy days and low solar declination values, corresponding, mainly, to the winter, autumn and spring seasons. Highest k_c values are concentrated during the summer season.

Thus, it can be concluded that EWB(60) dramatically improves the energy gain but at the expense of a reduction of the k_c value. However, it can be accepted that despite this lower k_c , these results are consistent with the requirement of constant irradiance profile for PV irrigation, suggesting that the EWB(60) structure is appropriate for such applications.

3.3 Energy losses

Operating conditions of the EWB(60) two halves are different since they are working at different incident irradiance ($G_{E,FRONT}$, $G_{W,FRONT}$, $G_{E,REAR}$ and $G_{W,REAR}$) and cell temperature ($T_{c,E}$ and $T_{c,W}$).

It must be considered that mismatching losses (MML) depend also on the non-uniformity of the rear side of the bifacial PV modules caused by both support structure shading (see Figure 4) and variations of the view factor from the ground to the different points of the PV module. In this regard, the experimental observations reported on [11] indicate that such MML represent about 0.1 – 0.2 % of the energy produced by a PV module.

Considering a hypothetical EWB(60) PV generator and

assuming that all the bifacial PV modules of the same string are installed on the same half, in addition that each one of the two halves of the PV generator are operated at the same maximum power point (MPP), the power delivered by each half, P_i , is given by:

$$P_i = P_i^* \cdot \frac{G}{G^*} \cdot [1 + \gamma(T_c - T_c^*)] \quad (2)$$

Where, subscript i designates the east or west side of the EWB(60) structure, the superscript “*” means Standard Test Conditions, T_c indicates cell temperature, γ is the power temperature coefficient of the PV module and G corresponds to the incident irradiance considering the module’s bifaciality (with bifaciality factor φ_p):

$$G = G_{FRONT} + \varphi_p \cdot G_{REAR} \quad (3)$$

$$\varphi_p = \frac{P_{REAR}^*}{P_{FRONT}^*} \quad (4)$$

The total power delivered by the EWB(60), P_{EWB} , is defined by the sum of the two halves:

$$P_{EWB} = P_W + P_E \quad (5)$$

In irrigation applications, PV generators are generally connected to a single frequency converter which integrates just one maximum power point tracker (MPPT). Since the MPP voltage varies with both irradiance and cell temperature, the MPP voltage of the two PV generator halves is different. Then, electrical mismatching losses appear, and Eq. (2) must be corrected. In accordance with [6], the electrical mismatching losses (F_{ML}) are obtained as the difference between the power obtained with two and one MPPT:

$$F_{ML} = \frac{P_{EWB} - P_{MPP}^{EWB}}{P_{EWB}} \quad (6)$$

where P_{MPP}^{EWB} represents the PV power considering just one MPPT for both EWB(60) halves and is obtained as the sum of both halves, as done in Eq. (5). In P_{MPP}^{EWB} each half operates at a voltage given by the weighted average of the corresponding values of the two halves, while P_{EWM} is the sum of the two halves operating at the corresponding voltage given by their both irradiance and cell temperature. Figure 7 illustrates the daily energy losses derived from the recorded data by the EWB(60) prototype. Each single point represents the total losses of a particular day. It can be observed that energy losses rise in the summer period (high declination values), where the mean value between the two equinoxes with positive declination (March and September) is $\mu(F_{ML}) = 1.66\%$.

Figure 7: Energy losses caused by mismatching due to the different operating conditions between the two EWB(60)

halves working both with a single MPPT. Each single point represents the losses for a particular day, measured over the entire year of recordings.

4 CONCLUSIONS

A prototype of a new PV generator concept, integrating bifacial PV modules, has been conceived as a ground-mounted structure with half of the PV array oriented to the east and the other half to the west, both parts with the same tilt angle ($\beta = 60$) and separated to allow that the PV modules' rear sides obtain a good irradiation uptake.

The so-called East-West Bifacial EWB(60) prototype has been tested at coordinates 40.39N, -3.63W in Madrid for a full year using two bifacial PV modules modified as reference modules to measure front and rear irradiances, and cell temperature. The experiment has allowed to characterize the performance of the EWB(60) structure in terms of energy gain, constancy index and energy losses caused by mismatching between the two halves of such PV generator.

The results show that EWB(60) increases energy production in terms of solar irradiation by 21.5% during the irrigation period compared to the same structure concept but using monofacial PV modules (the so-called Delta $\Delta S(60)$ structure).

The constancy index obtained by the experiment for clear sky days during the summer period (namely irrigation period) presents a mean value of 0.88, achieving a maximum figure of 0.94. The results are lower than those obtained by the $\Delta S(60)$ structure, but are consistent with the requirement for a constant irradiance profile for PV irrigation, suggesting that the EWB(60) structure is appropriate for such applications.

Finally, the energy losses due to the mismatching between both east and west halves of the PV generator have been characterized, yielding a mean value during the irrigation period of 1.66%.

These preliminary results open the door to a widespread use of EWB(60) structures for PV irrigation and future lines of work will be explored for the development of energy production simulation tools and their validation with full-scale prototypes.

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